

Does Location Matter? Inequalities in Specialist Palliative Home Care

A Comparative Analysis of Urban and Rural Patient Populations in Bavaria, Germany

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Background: Research suggests that patients are admitted to Specialist Palliative Home Care (SPHC) in crisis-ridden situations and too late in the disease trajectory. SPHC teams in Germany vary widely in structure and process and in relation to urban and rural settings.

Aim: To describe differences of patient characteristics, health status, symptom burden and use of other (palliative) care services on admission to SPHC teams in rural and urban areas.

Methods: Secondary analysis of a prospective cross-sectional multicentre study in four SPHC-teams (2 rural/ 2 urban). Information was extracted from electronic medical records: age, sex, disease categories, care degree, palliative care phase, Australian Karnofsky Performance Score (AKPS), residency on admission, survival, care by a specialist, 24-hour caregiver, utilization of care services (hospice care, physiotherapy, psychologist, social worker, medical supply store, support for parenteral drug application). In addition, self-assessment of symptom burden and problems was used at the start of care in the SPHC on the digital version of the Integrated Palliative Care Outcome Scale (eIPOS). The median total score was compared between urban and rural patients. Descriptive analysis and logistic regression with backward selection were performed.

Results: 593 patients (urban n=202, rural n=391) were included. No significant differences in age or gender were observed between rural and urban patients. On admission, rural SPHC-teams were significantly more likely than urban teams to care for patients in the deteriorating, dying, or unstable palliative phases. The odds ratios were 29.0 for the deteriorating phase (95% CI: 14.8–55.4), 19.0 for the dying phase (95% CI: 6.4–58.4), and 9.0 for the unstable phase (95% CI: 4.7–16.9) [$p < 0.0001$]. Additionally, patients in rural areas were twice as likely to live in nursing homes at the time of SPHC admission [$p=0.0086$]. Patients in the urban setting starting SPHC services were more likely than their rural counterparts to have access to resources such as 24-hour nursing [$OR=4$; $p=0.039$], hospice care [$OR=8$; $p<0.0001$] and medical supply stores [$OR=2$; $p=0.046$]. Other variables included in the analysis did not have a significant effect. eIPOS scores were higher in rural patients (median of the total score 29, range 14-47) than in urban patients (median of the total score 22, range 6-42). This suggests that at the beginning of SPHC care, rural patients have a higher symptom burden.

Conclusion: Our results suggest that patients in rural areas suffer from higher symptom burden and are more in crisis-like situations when starting SPHC and are more likely to be in nursing homes compared to patients in urban areas.